

Acidoid Behaviour of Charcoal as a Function of its Oxygen Complexes. Part VII. Formation of Oxygen Complexes and Development of Surface Acidity on Treatment with Nitric Acid

Balwant Rai Puri, (Miss) Sunila Singh, and O. P. Mahajan

Treatment of sugar charcoal, irrespective of the history of its formation, with concentrated nitric acid results in the fixation of an appreciable amount of oxygen, most of which on high-temperature evacuation is given off as carbon dioxide and has been termed as CO₂-complex. The treatment results in a considerable increase of surface acidity which is almost equivalent to the CO₂-complex formed on the surface. This offers some insight into the mechanism of base adsorption and cation-exchange capacity of charcoal. The treatment also results in making the surface hydrophilic as it increases greatly the moisture-sorption capacity throughout the entire range of vapour pressure. The increase at higher vapour pressures appears to be due to the formation of new micropores and that at lower vapour pressures due to the interaction of water vapour and active sites provided by the CO₂-complex by a mechanism involving hydrogen bonding. The heat of immersion in water also increases considerably, the increase on an average being about 4 kcal. per mole of CO₂-complex, which is of the same order as the heat of dissolution of CO₂ in water.

A considerable amount of work has been reported¹⁻¹⁹ in recent years on the effect of treatment of charcoal and carbon blacks with oxygen and oxidising agents, such as nitric acid, potassium permanganate, sodium hypochlorite, chlorine water, potassium persulphate, and ferric chloride, on the development of surface acidity, dispersibility, and lyophilic character of the products.

The alterations in surface characteristics have been attributed to the formation of polar functional groups, such as phenolic, carboxylic, and the like^{2,3,5,8,18}, but the evidence

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2. Donnet and Henrich, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1960, 1609.
3. Donnet *et al.*, *Compt. rend.*, 1961, 252, 1146.
4. Donnet *et al.*, *J. chim. phys.*, 1963, 60, 426.
5. Lygin *et al.*, *Kolloid Zhur.*, 1960, 22, 334.
6. Kiselev *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1961, 23, 582.
7. Kiselev *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1962, 24, 195.
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11. Weller and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 4155.
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14. Puri *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1958, 35, 181.
15. Puri *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1961, 38, 135.
16. Puri and Mahajan, *ibid.*, 1962, 39, 262.
17. *Idem*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1962, 741.
18. Hofmann and Ohlerich, *Angew. Chem.*, 1950, 62, 16.
19. Garten and Weiss, *Rev. Pure & Appl. Chem.*, 1957, 7, 69.

is by no means convincing and the application of principles of organic chemistry to the reactions of surface compounds has been rightly questioned²⁰. Puri *et al.*²¹⁻²⁴, on the other hand, are of the view that the acidity of carbons is due to the existence of a layer of carbon dioxide, held chemically or quasi-chemically on the surface, and may be termed as CO₂-complex. The treatment with oxidising agents simply extends this surface complex and therefore enhances surface acidity and polarity of the carbon. Cole and Dannenberg²⁵ from infrared examination of a number of carbon blacks adduced some evidence for the existence of an adsorbed layer of carbon dioxide. Studebaker²⁶ has rightly pointed out the desirability of pursuing this lead to determine the amount, stability, and nature of this adsorbed layer. The present communication describes the formation of surface oxygen complexes on treatment of sugar charcoal, outgassed at various temperatures, with nitric acid and the influence of these complexes on surface acidity, moisture-adsorption capacity, and heat of immersion of the product.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar charcoal, prepared in the manner described earlier²⁷, was used as such (when it is referred to as 'original' charcoal) as well as after outgassing at 300°, 500°, 600°, 900°, and 1200°.

Treatment with Nitric Acid.—Charcoal (5 g.), mixed with a certain amount of pure nitric acid and in a 250-ml beaker, was heated on a low Bunsen flame until the volume had been reduced to 5 ml. The contents were then transferred to a filter paper over a funnel and the residual charcoal was washed exhaustively with hot distilled water till the filtrate was free of nitrate ions. The material was dried first in air and then in an air-oven at 110°.

Determination of the Oxygen.—The amount of chemisorbed oxygen and the form in which it was evolved (as CO₂, CO, and H₂O) were determined in the manner described earlier^{21,27}.

Base-adsorption Capacity.—The maximum base-adsorption capacity (*i. e.*, total acidity) was determined as before²⁴ by mixing charcoal (1g.) with 0.2*N*-Ba(OH)₂ solution (100 ml) and heating the suspension (by placing the tightly corked bottles in a boiling water bath) for 8 hr. The capacity of charcoal to adsorb ammonia from aqueous suspension was also measured as before²⁸ by mixing charcoal (1 g.) with 0.4*N*-NH₄OH solution (100 ml) and shaking the suspension for 24 hr.

The pH-titration curves were also determined using, Ba(OH)₂ as the titrant²⁹.

20. Boehm *et al.*, 'Proc. Third Carbon Conf., 1957, Buffalo, U.S.A., Pergamon Press, 1959, 1, 241.

21. Puri *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 758.

22. Puri *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1958, 50, 1071.

23. Puri, Proc. Fifth Carbon Conf., 1961, Pennsylvania, U.S.A., Pergamon Press, 1962, 1, 165.

24. Puri and Bansal, *Journal Carbon*, 1964, in press.

25. Paper presented at the Joint Meeting of the ACS and CIS, Rubber Divisions, Montreal, Canada, May, 1957.

26. *Rubber Rev.*, Rubber Chemistry and Technology, 1957, 30, 1400.

27. Puri *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4880.

28. Puri and Mahajan, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 586.

29. Puri *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1957, 34, 367.

Water Isotherms, Surface Area, and Heat of Immersion.—Water-adsorption isotherms were determined³⁰ at 25°. Surface areas were calculated from the water isotherms³¹⁻³². The heat of immersion in water was measured as described before²¹.

DISCUSSION

The amount of oxygen chemisorbed and the form in which it is evolved (as CO₂, CO, and H₂O) in case of the various samples of charcoal, before and after treatment with nitric acid, are recorded in Table I. Each sample shows a considerable increase in the oxygen content; most of the new oxygen comes off as carbon dioxide, some as carbon monoxide, and little or none as water. The chemisorbed oxygen is seen to increase with increase in quantity of nitric acid used up to 30 ml/g. It was not possible to use large quantities as the product, even on using 30 ml, had become highly dispersed and difficult of recovery as it passed completely through the filter paper. Incidentally, the original as well as 300°-outgassed charcoal were burnt off more or less completely on treatment with nitric acid and therefore no data in these cases could be available.

TABLE I
Surface oxygen complexes formed on charcoal on treatment with different amounts of nitric acid.

HNO ₃ used. (ml/g).	Oxygen evolved (mg./g.) as			†Total oxygen evolved. (mg./g.).	Oxygen chemi- sorbed by charcoal (mg./g.).	Net loss in wt.
	CO ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ O.			
A. 500°-outgassed charcoal.						
0‡	9.6	48.9	50.4	108.9	..	..
10	91.5	47.9	48.9	188.3	79.4	12.72%
15	114.4	49.5	50.6	214.5	105.6	17.41
20	185.1	48.9	49.4	283.4	174.5	21.69
30	197.8	49.7	50.3	297.8	188.9	..
B. 600°-outgassed charcoal.						
0‡	Nil	25.2	45.3	70.5	..	..
10	92.1	59.4	44.8	196.3	125.8	..
15	111.5	66.6	45.7	223.8	153.3	..
20	124.1	67.0	45.4	236.5	168.0	..
30	161.3	75.3	45.9	282.5	212.0	..
C. 900°-outgassed charcoal.						
0‡	Nil	10.2	Nil	10.2	..	..
10	94.1	32.4	..	126.5	116.3	8.30
15	131.1	58.3	..	189.4	179.2	16.22
20	162.4	67.6	..	230.0	219.8	17.33
30	185.6	75.4	..	261.0	250.8	..
D. 1200°-outgassed charcoal.						
0‡	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	..	..
10	89.4	34.6	..	124.0	124.0	18.40
15	113.2	58.1	..	171.3	171.3	29.31
20	134.4	67.1	..	201.5	201.5	33.73
30	161.4	74.3	..	235.7	235.7	..

*The loss in weight could not be determined as colloidal solution of carbon was formed.

†Evolved as CO₂, CO, and H₂O.

‡Refers to that without treatment with HNO₃.

30. Puri *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 841.

31. Puri and Sharma, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1956, 15B, 178.

32. McDermot and Arnell, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 492.

The net loss in weight, obtained after making necessary allowance for increase in weight due to the chemisorption of oxygen, is shown in the last column. The interaction of charcoal and nitric acid involves not only surface oxidation but also combustion.

Surface acidity of charcoal (Table II) also increases with increase in the CO_2 -complex. For example, the $p\text{H}$ value falls, in some cases from neutral or even alkaline range, to as low as 2.2-2.6. The barium hydroxide value rises from a very low value, or even in some cases from zero, to as high as 1000-1200 m.e./100 g. This is probably the maximum value of acidity of any carbon ever reported. The ammonium hydroxide value, although appreciable, is not so high. This is evidently due to the fact that ammonia, being a weaker base, cannot push the neutralisation of the charcoal 'acidoid' to completion.

TABLE II

Surface acidity of charcoal in relation to the amount of CO_2 -complex.

HNO_3 used (ml/g.).	* $p\text{H}$.	† CO_2 -complex.	† $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ neutralised.	†Ammonia neutralised.
A. 500°-outgassed charcoal.				
0†	4.9	60.0	57.6	..
10	3.7	571.0	561.6	255.8
15	3.1	715.0	725.6	324.2
20	..	1156.9	1145.3	499.6
30	2.2	1236.2	1265.0	535.7
B. 600°-outgassed charcoal.				
0†	7.0	Nil	Nil	..
10	3.9	575.0	563.5	256.6
15	3.3	696.9	681.6	302.3
20	2.9	775.0	763.2	336.6
30	2.5	1008.2	1029.0	465.3
C. 900°-outgassed charcoal.				
0†	7.8	Nil	Nil	...
10	3.7	588.2	602.2	..
15	2.9	810.4	803.2	357.8
20	2.6	1015.0	1035.1	472.2
30	2.4	1160.7	1184.0	517.7
D. 1200°-outgassed charcoal.				
0†	8.5	Nil	Nil	..
10	3.7	558.7	564.6	252.4
15	3.2	707.5	719.5	302.6
20	2.8	840.0	850.3	..
30	2.6	1008.7	1024.4	460.9

*Values refer to aqueous suspension.

†Values expressed in m.e./100 g.

†Refers to that without treatment with HNO_3 .

The most interesting part of the data, however, is that the amount of barium hydroxide neutralised by charcoal, irrespective of its initial state or history of the treatment, is fairly close to the amount of the CO_2 -complex, *i.e.*, the amount of carbon dioxide evolved on high-temperature evacuation, when expressed in similar units. The importance of this

complex in influencing surface acidity is further emphasised by the data presented in Table III in which the base-adsorption capacities (b. a. c.) of 500- and 900°-outgassed charcoals treated with 30 ml of nitric acid/g. after evacuation at gradually increasing temperatures are recorded. It is seen that the value decreases with increase in the temperature of evacuation and that the decrease at a particular temperature is almost equivalent to the CO₂-complex eliminated at that temperature and ultimately when this complex is eliminated completely at 700°, the charcoal loses this property altogether even though it still retains some oxygen (about 4.5%) disposed of as carbon monoxide.

TABLE III

Decrease in the amount of Ba(OH)₂ neutralised by 500°- and 900°- outgassed charcoals treated with HNO₃ (30 ml/g.) after outgassing at various temperatures in relation to the amount of CO₂ evolved at each temperature.

Outgassing temp.	*Ba(OH) ₂ neutralised.	*Decrease in Ba(OH) ₂ neutralised.	*CO ₂ evolved on outgassing.
A. 500°-outgassed charcoal.			
Room temp.	1265.0	Nil	Nil
300°	696.6	568.4	557.7
400°	426.3	838.7	816.4
500°	88.4	1176.6	1141.3
700°	Nil	1265.0	1234.6
1000°	..	1265.0	1232.8
1200°	..	1265.0	1236.2
B. 900°-outgassed charcoal.			
Room temp.	1184.0	Nil	Nil
300°	526.7	657.3	642.0
400°	401.2	782.8	767.8
500°	207.3	976.7	997.5
550°	156.8	1033.2	1045.8
700°	Nil	1184.0	1165.6
1000°	..	1184.0	1163.8
1200°	..	1184.0	1160.7

*Values expressed in m.e./100 g.

This agreement cannot be due to presence of a carboxylic or a lactone group^{2,5,16,19} since in that case one mole (and not one equivalent as is actually the case) of carbon dioxide would have been evolved for each equivalent of alkali neutralised. Moreover, the existence of carboxylic groups has been inferred mainly on the basis of IR analysis, but it has been rightly pointed out²⁰ that in the case of carbons, IR spectra can only be of limited help and that usually there are more than one ways in which the wide absorption bands can be interpreted.

The data presented in Tables II and III support the conclusion previously reported^{21,24,29} that carbons owe their surface acidity to chemically or quasi-chemically adsorbed layer of carbon dioxide by virtue of which these undergo surface ionisation

on coming in contact with water, yielding hydrogen ions directed towards the liquid phase, as represented below:

the circle representing the charcoal surface.

Assuming molecular area of carbon dioxide (solidified) to be equal to $14.1 \text{ \AA}^2$, it can be shown by simple calculations from the knowledge of surface areas of the various charcoals (Table IV) that the surface coverage remains well within a monolayer even on an intensive treatment with nitric acid.

TABLE IV

Water-adsorption isotherms of charcoals in relation to CO₂-complex and surface area.

Sample.	CO ₂ - complex (m.c./100g.).	Surface area (m ² /g.).	Amount of water vapour adsorbed at R. V. P. (g./100 g.)							
			0.014.	0.181.	0.277.	0.384.	0.507.	0.680.	0.909.	0.987.
600°-outgassed charcoal,										
A	Nil	394.6	1.05	1.50	2.58	4.00	8.60	10.35	11.65	12.38
B	1008.2	438.4	7.70 (13.10)	9.76 (15.84)	11.07 (15.94)	12.76 (16.45)	15.38	19.25	26.02	34.30
900°-outgassed charcoal.										
A	Nil	410.3	0.82	1.45	1.74	3.10	10.60	11.95	13.10	13.65
B	1160.7	502.2	8.90 (14.22)	10.81 (16.27)	12.40 (18.50)	14.40 (19.12)	17.32	21.20	30.69	40.30
1200°-outgassed charcoal.										
A	Nil	414.1	0.80	1.43	1.72	2.82	10.89	13.22	14.30	15.15
B	1008.7	575.2	8.50 (14.70)	11.31 (18.48)	12.42 (19.93)	14.00 (20.07)	17.62	19.98	26.75	31.65
Charcoal steam-activated at 1000°.										
	Nil	943.4	3.75	6.78	11.50	14.12	15.06	29.22	37.52	45.85

N. B. A and B refer respectively to samples before and after treatment.

The chemical evidence for the existence of carboxylic group, as offered by Donnet *et al.*², is based on refluxing the carbon with calcium acetate and estimating acetic acid liberated thereby. But this reaction can easily be interpreted on the basis of the above mechanism of surface ionisation, as shown by the following stoichiometric equation:

The reaction of some of the charcoals with calcium acetate was actually studied in these investigations and not only the amount of acetic acid liberated was found to be very close to the total acidity value, but an equivalent amount of calcium, estimated in the manner described elsewhere²³, was found to be retained by the charcoal.

The pH-titration curves of the nitric acid-treated charcoals with barium hydroxide afforded fairly sharp and distinct end points. The neutralisation values as read from the curves were fairly close to those obtained by direct titrations (Table III).

The data regarding water-adsorption isotherms (25°) before and after treatment with 30 ml of HNO₃/g. are shown in Table IV. It is evident that the formation of CO₂-complex enhances the water-sorption capacity considerably throughout the entire range of vapour pressures. The increase at comparatively low relative vapour pressures is manifold and not merely two-fold or so, as has been reported for carbon blacks⁷ under similar treatments. The data for the water isotherm, obtained on activating sugar charcoal in steam at the optimum temperature of 1000°, are also included in the same table. The simple treatment with nitric acid thus places at our disposal a more convenient method for preparing a better water-adsorbent charcoal, particularly from atmospheres of lower relative humidity.

After correcting for increase in moisture adsorption, which may be expected from increase of surface area, the increase in the sorption of water per mole of CO₂-complex at relative vapour pressures up to 0.38 (up to which capillary condensation may not take place to a noticeable extent) was calculated. The values (included in Table IV in parantheses) indicate roughly sorption up to one mole of water per mole of CO₂-complex. This shows that each site containing a CO₂-complex can hold about one mole of water, in addition to the ordinary moisture-sorption capacity of the carbon, probably by a mechanism of hydrogen bonding. The results also indicate that the sorption at such sites proceeds in the form of 'clumps' or 'clusters'³⁴ of water molecules which grow in size with increase in relative vapour pressure up to a stage preceding capillary condensation.

TABLE V

Heats of immersion in water of the various samples of charcoal before and after treatment with nitric acid.

Samples outgassed at.	Surface area (m ² /g.).		CO ₂ -complex (m.o./100 g.).		Heat of immersion in water (cal./100 g.).		*Increase in heat of immersion (kcal./ mole CO ₂ -complex).
	A.	B.	A.	B.	A.	B.	
500°	420.7	487.8	60.0	1236.2	456.7	2887.8	4.05
600°	394.6	436.4	Nil	1008.2	410.2	2375.0	3.82
900°	410.3	502.3	„	1160.7	398.1	2922.1	4.20
1200°	414.1	575.2	„	1008.7	404.4	2570.3	3.97

*After correcting for increase in surface area.

N, B. A and B referred to as in Table IV.

The heats of immersion in water of the various samples of charcoal before and after treatment with nitric acid (30 ml./g.) are recorded in Table V. The value increases appreciably in proportion to CO₂-complex in every case. This further confirms that the presence of CO₂-complex renders the surface hydrophilic in proportion to its concentration.

34. Pari *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1958, 17B, 188.

35. Pierce and Smith, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1950, 54, 784.

The increase in heat of immersion per mole of CO_2 -complex was calculated after making allowance for the increase of surface area. It is seen (last column) that on an average 4 kcal. of heat is evolved on coming in contact with water of 1 mole of CO_2 -complex. It is of interest to note that this value is of the same order as the heat of dissolution of carbon dioxide (4.76 kcal.) in water.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
CHANDIGARH-3.

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